

International Journal of Human Resource & Industrial Research (IJHRIR)

ISSN: 2349 –3593 (Online), ISSN: 2349 –4816 (Print)

Available online at:

<http://www.arseam.com/content/volume-1-issue-2-june-2014>

Email: editor@arseam.com

Instructions for authors and subscription information:

MANAGING EMOTIONS: A STUDY OF TOP AND MIDDLE LEVEL MANAGERS OF POLLUTION CONTROL BOARD OF BHOPAL CITY

***Dr Priyanka Verma**

Assistant Professor,
Maulana Azad National Institute of Technology, Bhopal, India

Abstract:

The ability of managing emotions effectively is the important part of emotional intelligence. Regulating emotions, responding appropriately and responding to the emotions of others are integral aspect of emotional management. When the matter is related to happiness and success in life, emotional intelligence (EQ) matters a lot. Emotional intelligence helps an individual to build better relationships, succeed at work. It also helps in achieving one's career and personal goals. The present study has a qualitative approach done through questionnaire which were conducted with top and middle management in order to investigate the role of emotional intelligence at workplace and its impact on relation with coworkers in correlation with its impact on self. The findings confirmed the hypotheses formulated, The research has shown how the emotional intelligence reflects the working in the organization.

Key words: emotions, intelligence, integral aspect of, EQ,

INTRODUCTION

Peter Salovey and John Mayer, originally used the term "emotional intelligence" Later, they revised their definition of emotional intelligence. Emotional intelligence is thus defined as: *The ability to perceive emotion, integrate emotion to facilitate thought, understand emotions, and to regulate emotions to promote personal growth*. Another prominent personality Reuven Bar-On, the originator of the term "emotion quotient" had a slightly different outlook and defined it as emotional intelligence is concerned with understanding oneself and others, relating to people, and adapting to and coping with the immediate surroundings to be more successful in dealing with environmental demands .

Literature Review:

Personality, one's characteristic pattern of thinking, feeling, and acting, has been explored using a variety of theories including psychoanalytic, humanistic, social-cognitive, and trait theory. In a longitudinal study of American adults, Costa and McCrea (1982) found that for the majority of people, personality at age 30 was predictive of personality at age 80.

Several trait theorists have proposed models of personality based on the factor analyses of traits expressed through personality inventories. For example, Hans and Sybil Eysenck's model of personality outlined two genetically influenced dimensions of personality: introversion-extroversion and stability-instability (Myers, 1998). The Big Five Personality Factor Model, often called the "Big Five" or the "Five Factor Model", is an empirically derived model of personality based on the early work on traits by Gordon Allport, Raymond Cattell, and Hans and Sybil Eysenck. It proposes that personality can be factored into five dimensions: neuroticism, extraversion, openness, agreeableness, and conscientiousness.

One of the most applied constructs which emotional intelligence has been associated with is that of leadership. Mandell and Pherwani found that level of emotional intelligence (as measured by the Bar-On Emotion Quotient Inventory) was significantly related to transformational leadership style ($R = .50$). The foremost contributor to the area of emotional intelligence and leadership is Daniel Goleman, Goleman posits that leaders high in emotional intelligence are key to organizational success; leaders must have the capacity to sense employees' feelings about their work environments, to intervene when problems arise, to manage their own emotions in order to gain the trust of the employees, and to understand the political and social conventions within an organization.

Daniel Goleman asserts that no gender differences in E.I. exist, admitting that while men and women may have different profiles of strengths and weaknesses in different areas of emotional intelligence, their overall levels of E.I. are equivalent. However, studies by Mayer and Geher, Mayer, Caruso, and Salovey, and more recently Mandell and Pherwani have found that women are more likely to score higher on measures of emotional intelligence than men, both in professional and personal settings.

The discrepancy may be due to measurement choice. Brackett and Mayer found that females scored higher than males on E.I. when measured by a performance measure (the Mayer-Salovey-Caruso Emotional Intelligence Test). However, when using self-report measures such as the Bar-On Emotion Quotient Inventory (EQ-i) and the Self-Report Emotional Intelligence Test (SREIT), they found no evidence for gender differences. Perhaps gender differences exist in emotional intelligence only when one defines E.I. in a purely cognitive manner rather than through a mixed perspective.

Several studies have found that emotional intelligence can have a significant impact on various elements of everyday living. Palmer, Donaldson, and Stough found that higher emotional intelligence was a predictor of life satisfaction. Additionally, Pelletier reported that people higher in emotional intelligence were also more likely to use an adaptive defence style and thus exhibited healthier psychological adaptation. Performance measures of emotional intelligence have illustrated that higher levels of E.I. are associated with an increased likelihood of attending to health and appearance, positive interactions with friends and family, and owning objects that are reminders of their loved ones. Mayer, Caruso, and Salovey found that higher emotional intelligence correlated significantly with higher parental warmth and attachment style, while others found that those scoring high in E.I. also reported increased positive interpersonal relationships among children, adolescents, and adults.

Advanced emotional intelligence can be beneficial in many areas of life. Main reasons behind the workplace being a logical setting for evaluating and improving emotional intelligence competencies are

1. Emotional intelligence competencies are critical for success in most jobs.
2. Many adults enter the workforce without the competencies necessary to succeed or excel at their job.

3. Employers already have the established means and motivation for providing emotional intelligence training.
4. Most adults spend the majority of their waking hours at work.

A strong interest in the professional applications of emotional intelligence is apparent in the way organizations have embraced E.I. ideas. The American Society for Training and Development, for example, has published a volume describing guidelines for helping people in organizations cultivate emotional intelligence competencies which distinguish outstanding performers from average ones.

APPLICATIONS OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE IN THE ORGANIZATIONS

EI has a number of applications in both business and non business organisations in following areas:

1.Filling Organisation Positions

In an organization where different types of positions are created in such case meeting the requirement of various characteristics of individual such as age, experience and personality etc.

2.Work Life

Work life relates to the impact of work on people as well as on organizational effectiveness and the idea of participation in organizational problem solving and decision making. High EI is very relevant of improving the quality of work life.

3.Credibility Of Managers

It means what one says and does. When there is a difference between what one says and does credibility gap exist.

4.Leadership Effectiveness

If a person influences his followers for productivity on long term basis he is an effective leader. A leader with high EI has the following features--ability to regulate emotions, ability to analyse emotions, emotional facilitation of thinking, ability to express emotions

5.Effective Communications

Communication is effective when the sender and receiver of the message under the communication process have same meaning to it. EI helps in making communication effective by--Increasing self awareness, Expression of feelings, Clarifying interpersonal feelings, Increasing the accuracy of interpersonal perception

6.Handling Frustrations

EI helps in handling frustration like aggression, withdrawal and compromise both at work as well as in day to day life. EI helps in choosing the most desirable way of overcoming frustration.

7.Stress Management

It is helpful in diluting--Individual stress, Group stress, Organizational stress, Extra organizational stress at work place as well as in modern life.

8. Conflict Resolution

EI helps in conflict resolution and also in creating non-arousal of conflicts .

9. Managing emotions

Managing emotions at workplace and in other fields of life is essential for success which can be done by using E.I.

10. Understanding desired emotional skills:

Helpful in the identification of different types of emotional skills like--Self awareness, Managing emotions, Empathy, Cooperation, Resolving conflicts for employees performing different jobs at work place

11. Recognising emotions

Ability to recognise one's emotions enables a person to manage them by emphasising on positive emotion and controlling negative emotion.

12. Developing higher self esteem

High self esteem is important because it not only gives a person a realistic confidence within himself but also the ability to handle the problems.

13. Learning to attain self defined goals

E.Q helps in defining and in attaining these goals.

14. Dealing with emotional upset

For people with high EI emotional upset period may be short and people with low EI this period will be long.

15. Coping with anger

E.Q. helps in dealing with anger. It helps in avoiding major actions during the period of anger, in analysing the cause of anger and the situations under which anger takes place.

16. Practicing emotional quality management

Hein defined EQM as the management of emotional intelligence in an organization. EQM requires the management of certain emotional competencies such as the ability to take responsibility for one's emotions, to use emotions as a source of productive energy. to identify and label specific feelings in oneself and others.

EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE MODELS:

Theorists such as Thorndike and Gardner paved the way in the field of emotional intelligence. Emotional intelligence is conceptualized from one of two perspectives: ability or mixed model. Ability models consider emotional intelligence as a pure form of mental ability and hence as a pure intelligence. In contrast, mixed models of emotional intelligence combine mental ability with personality characteristics such as optimism and well-being (Mayer, 1999).

Bar-On: A Mixed Model of Emotional Intelligence

Reuven Bar-On model of emotional intelligence is related to the *potential* for performance and success, which is considered as process-oriented (Bar-On, 2002) focussing on an array of emotional and social abilities. In his model, five components of emotional intelligence: intrapersonal, interpersonal, adaptability, stress management, and general mood are discussed along with sub-components. According to Bar-On emotional intelligence develops over time which can be improved through training,

programming, and therapy (Bar-On, 2002). Bar-On hypothesizes that higher than average E.Q. individuals are in general more successful in facing pressures and meeting environmental demands and any deficiency in emotional intelligence leads to unsucccess and emotional problems. Problems in coping with one's environment is common among those individuals who lack in reality testing, problem solving, stress tolerance, and impulse control.

Bar-On's Model of Emotional Intelligence

Components	Sub-Components
Intrapersonal	Self Regard Emotional Self-Awareness Assertiveness Independence Self-Actualization
Interpersonal	Empathy Social Responsibility Interpersonal Relationship
Adaptability	Reality Testing Flexibility Problem Solving
Stress Management	Stress Tolerance Impulse Control
General Mood Components	Optimism Happiness

RESEARCH METHEDODOLOGY

Objectives of Study:

1. To determine applicability of emotional intelligence at workplace
2. To identify the response of the managers towards emotional intelligence in the organizations at various situations.

Methods of data collection:

The primary data is collected with the help of the interviews by the top and middle level managers of Madhya Pradesh Pollution Control Board. Secondary data is collected with the help of websites and books.

Sample Size: Sample size was 100 employees.

Source Of Information: The source of information are the managers of MPPCB. All of them belong to the top level and middle level of management.

Sampling : Sampling is the convenient sampling.

Statistical Technique : Correlation method is used for the analysis of the interpretation The Reuben Bar-On model of emotional intelligence has been referred for the current study.

HYPOTHESES:

1. **HO₁:** Managers having better emotional intelligence do not have better tendency to overreaction to minor problems.
2. **HO₂:** Managers having high element of EQ don't have better response towards the behaviour of co-worker

3. **HO₃**: High EQ level managers do not show good reaction during a heated argument.
4. **HO₄**: Managers with high EQ level don't show criticism towards oneself after making mistake.
5. **HO₅**: High EQ level of managers has no relation with response towards confrontation.
6. **HO₆**: High EQ Level is not associated with better defining about self

Research Model:

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION:

The data collected has been analysed and interpreted by using correlation value in the following manner.

Table:1: Pearson Correlation Coefficient test results for the relation between Emotional Intelligence and Overreaction to minor problems

HO ₁		Emotional Intelligence
Overreaction to minor problems	Correlation Percentage	.58
	Level Of Significance	.05
	Number	100

The Pearson's positive correlation value indicates that managers having good level of emotional intelligence level have better command over the minor problems in comparison to the people having lower emotional intelligence level. According to Salovey's four branch model of emotional intelligence, they come in the fourth branch which is **Emotional Management**, it is the ability to react according to the situation. They understand the feelings of others. Hence the hypothesis that managers having better emotional intelligence do not have better tendency to overreaction to minor problems is rejected.

Table:2 Pearson Correlation Coefficient test results for the relation between Emotional Intelligence and Response towards the behaviour of co-worker

HO ₂		Emotional Intelligence
Response towards the behaviour of co-worker	Correlation Percentage	.54
	Level Of Significance	.05
	Number	100

The positive correlation value indicates that managers having high level of emotional intelligence level have better command over the minor problems in comparison to the people having lower emotional ,they have **intrapersonal component** of emotional self awareness, have the component of **stress management** and have impulse control. Whereas people having lower level of EQ lack the component of **adaptability** that is problem solving.This leads to the rejection ofthe hypothesis that managers having high element of EQ don't have better response towards the behaviour of co-worker.

Table:3 Pearson Correlation Coefficient test results for the relation between Emotional Intelligence and Reaction during a heated argument

HO ₃		Emotional Intelligence
Reaction during a heated argument	Correlation Percentage	.43
	Level Of Significance	.05
	Number	100

Correlation value showing positive sign indicates that managers having good level of emotional intelligence level have better impulse control in comparison to the people having lower emotional intelligence level as they have the component of **adaptability** i.e problem solving, reality testing and flexibility.Thus it can be inferred that high EQ level managers show good reaction during a heated argument.

Table:4 Pearson Correlation Coefficient test results for the relation between Emotional Intelligence and Criticism towards oneself after making mistake

HO ₄		Emotional Intelligence
Criticism towards oneself after making mistake	Correlation Percentage	.46
	Level Of Significance	.05
	Number	100

Higher EQ Level people have **the intrapersonal component** of assertiveness and independence so they have lesser component of criticism towards oneself after making mistake since they possess the intrapersonal component of self awareness and **good mood component** of happiness and optimism.The positive correlation value indicates that manager's high EQ level don't show criticism towards oneself after making mistake.

Table:5 Pearson Correlation Coefficient test results for the relation between Emotional Intelligence and Response to confrontation

HO ₅		Emotional Intelligence
Response to confrontation	Correlation Percentage	.38
	Level Of Significance	.05
	Number	100

The positive value of.38 is indicative of the fact that managers who disagree or strongly disagree regarding their response to confrontation have higher EQ level and hence they have the **interpersonal component** as well as they have the **adaptability component** of flexibility and the **stress management component**. Hence the hypothesis high EQ level of managers has no relation with response towards confrontation is rejected.

Table:6 Pearson Correlation Coefficient test results for the relation between Emotional Intelligence and Level of defining about self

HO ₆		Emotional Intelligence
Level of defining about self	Correlation Percentage	.36
	Level Of Significance	.05
	Number	100

High EQ level have easy time making friend **have interpersonal component** of interpersonal relationship LOWER EQ people have difficulty in making friends lack the **adaptability component** of flexibility people who do not trust easily lack the component of optimism. The positive correlation value indicates the rejection of the hypothesis that high EQ Level is not associated with better defining about self .

FINDINGS

- 1 Managers having good level of emotional intelligence level have better command over the minor problems in comparison to the people having lower emotional intelligence level
2. Managers having high level of emotional intelligence level have intrapersonal component of emotional self awareness, have the component of stress management and have impulse control.
- 3 Managers having good level of emotional intelligence level have better component of **adaptability** i.e problem solving, reality testing and flexibility..
4. Higher EQ Level people have assertiveness and independence so they have lesser component of criticism towards oneself after making mistake since they possess component of self awareness and **good mood component** of happiness and optimism..
5. Managers who disagree or strongly disagree regarding their response to confrontation have higher EQ level and hence they have the **adaptability component** of flexibility and the **stress management component**.
6. High EQ level have easy time making friend **have component** of interpersonal relationship .LOWER EQ managers lack the **adaptability component** of flexibility people who do not trust easily lack the component of optimism.

LIMITATIONS

1. The respondents are not available
2. The sample size is not sufficient
3. The responses given by the respondents are not fully correct

SUGGESTIONS

- 1.The organizations can use various models of emotional intelligence to know their employees
- 2.It can be used in training as well as in selection and recruitment.
- 3.It can also be used in training evaluation and career development of employees
- 4.It can help in developing good working conditions in the organization and better relationship among the employees.

5.It is mainly the duty of the top level management to see that the emotional intelligence is being properly implemented in the organization.For this they can hire the experts.

CONCLUSION

In today's world using the concept of emotional intelligence has become very crucial and essential, if the organizations want to survive in this cut throat competition.

Human resource is one of the important resource the organization has therefore it is also sometimes called human capital. Emotional intelligence is very important for the organization because it gives the employees a sense of job satisfaction and also helps in the retention of good employees. It helps in their career development and career planning.

There are various models of emotional intelligence that can be applied in the organization to make working environment good and healthy. It can be used from the beginning that is right from the recruitment and selection of the employees till their retirement. The organizations implementing emotional intelligence can grow faster than the organization not using it.

REFERENCES:

- 1.Bhattacharya,M,S and Sengupta,N(2007),Emotional IntelligencMyth orReality, Excel Books.
- 2.Davis ,M.,Stankov,L.&Roberts,R.D.(1998)Emotional Intelligence:In searchof an elusive construct,Journal of Personality ans Social Psychology,75,989-101
- 3.Rafaeli, A., and Sutton, R. I. (1987). 'The expression of emotion as part of the work role', Academy of Management Review, 12, 23-37.
- 4.Joseph, D.L. and Newman, D.A. (2010). 'Emotional intelligence: An integrative meta-analysis and cascading model', Journal of Applied Psychology, 95, 54-78
- 5.Mayer, J. D., Salovey, P., & Caruso, D. R. (2000). Models of emotional intelligence. R. J. Sternberg (Ed.). Handbook of Intelligence (pp. 396-420). Cambridge, England: Cambridge University Press.